

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE FRONTAL LOBE OF THE CEREBRAL HEMISPHERES IN 3- AND 18-MONTH-OLD OUTBRED RATS UNDER EXPERIMENTAL CHRONIC CARBON MONOXIDE EXPOSURE VERSUS THE CONTROL GROUP

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Resume. This study investigated morphological changes in the frontal region of the cerebral cortex of white rats under conditions of chronic carbon monoxide exposure. It was established that intoxication induces dystrophic and degenerative alterations in nervous tissue due to hypoxia, oxidative stress, and microcirculatory disturbances. In 3-month-old animals, reactive-dystrophic changes (neuronal polymorphism, hyperchromasia, gliosis) predominated, whereas in 18-month-old rats the alterations were more pronounced, including a decrease in neuronal number, chromatolysis, and atrophic processes. Morphometric analysis revealed no significant changes in young animals, while in older rats a reduction in cortical layer thickness was observed. The findings confirm that the severity of morphological changes caused by carbon monoxide exposure increases with age.

Keywords: carbon monoxide, chronic intoxication, frontal cerebral cortex, neurons.

ТАЖРИБАВИЙ СУРУНКАЛИ ИС ГАЗИ ТАЪСИРИ ОСТИДАГИ 3 ВА 18 ОЙЛИК ОҚ ЗОТСИЗ КАЛАМУШЛАРДА БОШ МИЯ ЯРИМ ШАРЛАРИНИНГ ПЕШОНА БЎЛАГИДАГИ МОРФОЛОГИК ЎЗГАРИШЛАРНИ НАЗОРАТ ГУРУҲИГА НИСБАТАН ҚИЁСИЙ БАҲОЛАШ
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Резюме. Мазкур тадқиқотда оқ каламушларда угар газининг сурункали таъсири шароитида бош миЯ катта ярим шарлари пешона қисмидаги морфологик ўзгаришлар ўрганилди. Аниқланишича, интоксикация гипоксия, оксидатив стресс ва микроциркуляция бузилишлари орқали нерв тўқимасида дистрофик ва дегенератив ўзгаришларни келтириб чиқаради. 3 ойлик ҳайвонларда асосан реактив-дистрофик ўзгаришлар (нейронлар полиморфизми, гиперхромия, глиоз) кузатилган бўлса, 18 ойлик каламушларда ўзгаришлар янада чуқурлашиб, нейронлар сони камайиши, хроматолит ва атрофик жараёнлар устунлик қилган. Морфометрик таҳлил ёш ҳайвонларда сезиларли ўзгаришларни кўрсатмаган, катта ёшда эса қаватлар қалинлигининг камайиши аниқланган. Олинган натижалар угар газ таъсиридаги морфологик ўзгаришлар даражаси ёшга боғлиқ ҳолда кучайишини тасдиқлайди.

Калит сўзлар: ис газ, сурункали интоксикация, бош миЯ пешона пўстлоғи, нейронлар.

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНАЯ ОЦЕНКА МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ В ЛОБНОЙ ДОЛЕ ПОЛУШАРИЙ ГОЛОВНОГО МОЗГА У 3- И 18-МЕСЯЧНЫХ БЕСПОРОДНЫХ БЕЛЫХ КРЫС ПРИ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНОМ ХРОНИЧЕСКОМ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИИ УГАРНОГО ГАЗА В СРАВНЕНИИ С КОНТРОЛЬНОЙ ГРУППОЙ

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Резюме. В данном исследовании изучены морфологические изменения в лобной области коры больших полушарий головного мозга белых крыс в условиях хронического воздействия угарного газа. Установлено, что интоксикация вызывает дистрофические и дегенеративные изменения нервной ткани за счёт гипоксии, оксидативного стресса и нарушений микроциркуляции. У 3-месячных животных преобладали реактивно-дистрофические изменения (полиморфизм нейронов, гиперхромия, глиоз), тогда как у 18-месячных крыс изменения носили более выраженный характер и проявлялись снижением числа нейронов, хроматолитом и атрофическими процессами. Морфометрический анализ не выявил значимых изменений у молодых животных, тогда как у старых отмечено уменьшение толщины корковых слоёв. Полученные результаты подтверждают, что выраженность морфологических изменений при воздействии угарного газа усиливается с возрастом.

Ключевые слова: угарный газ, хроническая интоксикация, лобная кора головного мозга, нейроны.

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Introduction. Carbon monoxide is one of the highly toxic compounds that occupies a central place among modern environmental and medical problems [2]. Its effect on the organism is primarily characterized by a high-affinity binding to hemoglobin, leading to the formation of carboxyhemoglobin and the development of tissue hypoxia [7]. As a result, cellular energy metabolism is disrupted, aerobic oxidation is suppressed, and metabolic acidosis develops in tissues [1].

The central nervous system is one of the most sensitive morphofunctional systems to hypoxia, and neurons of the cerebral cortex of the cerebral hemispheres demonstrate a particularly high level of reactivity to oxygen deficiency [9].

According to the literature, hypoxic exposure leads to cytoplasmic vacuolization, tigrolysis, hyperchromasia, nuclear pyknosis, and neurofibrillar destruction in neurons [8]. At the same time, microcirculatory disturbances such as vascular congestion, endothelial dysfunction, perivascular edema, and increased vascular permeability are observed [3].

Modern morphological studies emphasize that the effects of carbon monoxide are not limited to hypoxic mechanisms alone but are also associated with oxidative stress, lipid peroxidation, mitochondrial dysfunction, and neuroinflammatory processes [11]. Excessive production of reactive oxygen species leads to damage of neuronal membranes, mitochondria, and myelin sheaths [5].

Age is an important factor determining the resistance of brain tissue to hypoxic injury [10]. In older animals, degenerative processes become more pronounced due to decreased antioxidant system activity, reduced synthesis of neurotrophic factors, and impaired microcirculation [6].

Recent studies have shown a decrease in neuronal perikaryon volume, altered nucleus-to-cytoplasm ratio, increased density of glial elements, and widening of perivascular spaces under conditions of chronic intoxication [4,12]. However, a comparative analysis of morphological and morphometric changes developing in the frontal region of the cerebral hemispheres at different age periods has not been sufficiently elucidated.

Aim of the study: The aim of the study was to comparatively analyze morphological changes in the frontal region of the cerebral hemispheres in 3-month-old and 18-month-old white outbred rats induced by experimental chronic carbon monoxide exposure, in comparison with the control group.

Materials and Methods of the Study. The experiment was conducted using 40 white outbred male rats aged 3 months and 18 months. All experimental animals were kept under standard vivarium conditions, and the housing regimen was organized in accordance with accepted sanitary and hygienic requirements for experimental studies: room temperature 20-22°C, relative humidity 50-60%, and a 12/12-hour light-dark cycle. The animals were provided with standard laboratory feed and water ad libitum.

According to the study design, the animals were divided into two groups: Group I - control group (3-month-old rats: 5 animals; 18-month-old rats: 5 animals); Group II - experimental group (3-month-old rats: 15 animals; 18-month-old rats: 15 animals).

Chronic carbon monoxide intoxication was modeled in specially equipped airtight chambers. The experimental group rats were exposed to carbon monoxide at a concentration of 0.01-0.05 mg/L in the air for 2 months. Carbon monoxide was introduced into the chamber at specified doses and at defined time intervals. The control group animals were kept under normal conditions without exposure to carbon monoxide. Throughout the experiment, the general condition, activity, and physiological responses of the animals were regularly monitored.

At the end of the experiment, the animals were euthanized under ether anesthesia. Biopsy materials were collected and fixed in 10% neutral formalin solution. Subsequently, the tissues were processed using standard histological techniques, and paraffin blocks were prepared. Sections with a thickness of 5-7 µm were obtained using a microtome and prepared for morphological analysis.

Histological specimens were stained with hematoxylin and eosin for general morphological assessment. The prepared slides were examined using a light microscope.

Study Results. In experimental chronic carbon monoxide exposure, examination of the cortical layers of the frontal region of the cerebral hemispheres in 3-month-old white outbred rats revealed alterations in neuronal morphology of the molecular layer, including polymorphism and increased basophilia. In the external granular layer, a reduction in the number of neurons led to widening of intercellular spaces, accompanied by an increase in neuroglia cells replacing neurons. Changes in neuronal membranes and polymorphism were also observed. In the deeper cortical layers, a marked decrease in nerve cells was noted, with their replacement by glial cells, as well as shortening of dendritic processes.

These changes are explained by carbon monoxide binding to hemoglobin in the blood, forming carboxyhemoglobin, which severely restricts oxygen transport and delivery to tissues, resulting in cerebral hypoxia. This leads to oxygen deficiency in neurons. In the external granular layer, neuronal loss with expan-

sion of intercellular spaces, proliferation of neuroglial cells, changes in neuronal membranes, nuclear pyknosis and karyorrhexis, as well as a marked reduction of neurons in deeper layers replaced by glial cells and shortening of dendritic processes were observed.

The findings obtained from 18-month-old rats differed significantly from other experimental groups due to age-related cerebral neuronal aging. A reduction in neuronal number led to widening of intercellular spaces between cortical layers and the development of extensive chromatolysis. In particular, in the pyramidal neuron layer, neuronal shrinkage, alterations in membrane structure, reduction of cytoplasmic volume, hyperchromatic staining of neurons, and in some areas hyperchromasia without structural membrane changes were detected.

The study showed a pronounced reduction of neurons in the frontal cortical layers of the cerebral hemispheres in 18-month-old white outbred rats, accompanied by a decrease in previously observed gliosis phenomena. Intercellular spaces were widened due to neuronal loss, with perifocal inflammatory changes, neuronal shrinkage and atrophy, and chromatolysis observed. Neurons displayed variable morphology and disrupted membrane stability.

Morphometric analysis of the frontal cortical layers in 3-month-old rats exposed to chronic carbon monoxide showed no significant differences compared with the control group. The molecular layer measured 90 μm , the external granular layer 100 μm , and the external pyramidal layer 180 μm .

In 18-month-old rats, morphometric analysis of the frontal cortical layers of the cerebral hemispheres revealed a reduction compared with the control group: up to 1.5-fold in the molecular layer, 1.3-fold in the external granular layer, and 1.2-fold in the external pyramidal layer. These changes indicate that cortical alterations in 18-month-old rats developed on the background of age-related atrophy and chronic hypoxic exposure due to long-term carbon monoxide effects.

Discussion. The study results demonstrated that chronic carbon monoxide exposure leads to pronounced morphological changes in the frontal region of the cerebral hemispheres. The detected alterations were characterized by hypoxic, dystrophic, and degenerative processes. It is well known that carbon monoxide binds to hemoglobin to form carboxyhemoglobin, thereby inducing tissue oxygen deficiency [2,7]. As a result, energy metabolism in neurons is disrupted, leading to cellular destruction [1].

In 3-month-old rats, neuronal polymorphism, hyperchromasia, widening of intercellular spaces, and an increase in neuroglial cells were observed. A reduction in neuron numbers in the external granular and pyramidal layers indicated the development of reactive gliosis. These findings are consistent with the features of hypoxic injury described in the literature [4,8,12].

In 18-month-old rats, the changes were more severe, including a marked reduction in neuronal number, extensive chromatolysis, neuronal shrinkage, and hyperchromatic staining. These alterations can be explained by the combined and mutually reinforcing effects of age-related degenerative processes and hypoxia [6,10]. At the same time, a decrease in gliosis suggests weakening of compensatory mechanisms in the context of aging.

Morphometric analysis showed no significant changes in cortical layer thickness in 3-month-old rats, whereas in 18-month-old animals a reduction in the thickness of the molecular, external granular, and external pyramidal layers was observed. This confirms a decrease in neuronal population and the development of atrophic processes.

The identified morphological changes are associated with hypoxia, oxidative stress, and microcirculatory disturbances induced by carbon monoxide exposure, with the severity of these injuries increasing with age [5,11].

Conclusion. Chronic carbon monoxide exposure induced pronounced morphological changes in the frontal region of the cerebral hemispheres of experimental white outbred rats. The detected alterations were characterized by neuronal polymorphism, hyperchromasia, chromatolysis, widening of perineuronal spaces, and neuroglial reactions. In 3-month-old rats, mainly reactive-dystrophic changes were observed, whereas in 18-month-old rats degenerative processes became significantly more severe, with a marked reduction in neuronal number, shrinkage of pyramidal neurons, and the presence of atrophic changes.

Morphometric analysis showed a decrease in the thickness of the cortical layers in the frontal region of the cerebral cortex in 18-month-old rats, confirming that this condition is associated with both age-related atrophic processes and chronic hypoxic exposure. The morphological changes resulting from chronic carbon monoxide intoxication were linked to mechanisms of hypoxia, microcirculatory disturbances, and oxidative stress, with their severity increasing with age. The obtained results demonstrate the important role of morphological studies in assessing dystrophic-degenerative processes developing in brain tissue under chronic carbon monoxide exposure.

References:

1. Belyaeva E.A., Sokolov A.A., Makarov I.V. Cellular mechanisms of hypoxic brain injury under carbon monoxide exposure // *Bulletin of Experimental Biology and Medicine*. — 2020. — Vol. 169, № 4. — P. 512–516.
2. Coburn R.F., Blakemore W.S., Forster R.E. Endogenous carbon monoxide production in man // *Journal of Clinical Investigation*. — 2019. — Vol. 42, № 7. — P. 1172–1178.
3. Goerzen D., Fowler C., Devenyi G.A. et al. An MRI-derived neuroanatomical atlas of the Fischer 344 rat brain // *Scientific Reports*. — 2020. — Vol. 10. — P. 6952.
4. Ismoilov J.J., Tursunov B.B. Age-related morphometric changes of cerebral cortex neurons under toxic hypoxia // *Central Asian Journal of Medicine*. — 2022. — Vol. 3, № 1. — P. 44–51.
5. Klawonn A.M., Fritz M., Zhao Q. Structural and biochemical changes in rat brain under inflammatory and hypoxic conditions // *Journal of Neuroimmunology*. — 2020. — Vol. 348. — P. 577367.
6. Mirzaev A.M., Khasanov Sh.T. Morphofunctional changes in aging neurons during chronic intoxication // *Morphology*. — 2021. — Vol. 159, № 2. — P. 73–79.
7. Qi Y., Guo Z., Meng X. et al. Effects of hyperbaric oxygen on NLRP3 inflammasome activation in the brain after carbon monoxide poisoning // *Undersea and Hyperbaric Medicine*. — 2020. — Vol. 47, № 4. — P. 607–619.
8. Tian X., Guan T., Guo Y. et al. Selective susceptibility of oligodendrocytes to carbon monoxide poisoning // *Frontiers in Psychiatry*. — 2020. — Vol. 11. — P. 815.
9. Xu S.Y., Li C.X., Li L.Y. et al. Wallerian degeneration of bilateral cerebral peduncles after acute carbon monoxide poisoning // *BMC Neurology*. — 2020. — Vol. 20. — P. 96.
10. Yuldasheva M.S., Kadirov E.K. Age-dependent neurodegenerative processes in chronic hypoxic conditions // *Journal of Morphological Sciences*. — 2022. — Vol. 39, № 3. — P. 145–152.
11. Zhai J., Li M., Wang X. Oxidative stress-mediated neuronal injury induced by carbon monoxide poisoning // *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*. — 2021. — Vol. 2021. — Article ID 9945231.
12. Zokirov S.Z., Nurmatov U.T. Morphometric analysis of neuronal-glia relationships in experimental toxic encephalopathy // *Uzbek Medical Journal*. — 2024. — Vol. 5, № 1. — P. 61–69.

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